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RESEARCH ARTICLE

H3CPP: Boundary-Safe Coverage Path Planning for Multi-USV Operations in Irregular Coastal Environments

GIANNIS SPILIOPOULOS¹, (Graduate Student Member, IEEE), ELIAS XIDIAS¹,
AND DIMITRIS ZISSIS¹, (Senior Member, IEEE)

Department of Product and Systems Design Engineering, University of the Aegean, 84100 Ermoupoli, Greece

Corresponding author: Elias Xidias (xidias@aegean.gr)

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ABSTRACT As the need for persistent ocean monitoring grows, fleets of Uncrewed Surface Vessels (USVs) are a promising way to survey large marine protected areas with low operational cost. Their effectiveness, however, depends on solving a challenging multi-robot Coverage Path Planning (CPP) problem over complex coastal geometries while strictly respecting safety boundaries. This paper presents H3CPP, a CPP framework that leverages the H3 hierarchical hexagonal grid to discretize arbitrarily shaped marine areas, cluster them into connected subregions, and construct boundary-aware graphs on which Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) tours are computed. Each H3 cell is sized to match the nominal sensing footprint of a USV, and edges that intersect land or forbidden zones are exponentially penalized, encouraging safe paths that remain within the operational polygon. We evaluate H3CPP on seven benchmark polygonal maps and on a real-world coastal marina using 1–10 USVs. For a single USV in complex, non-convex environments, H3CPP achieves near-complete coverage (coverage ratio ≈ 1.0 of the target area) while avoiding boundary violations that occur with swath and spiral baselines, and reduces path length by up to 10% compared to these methods in the most irregular shapes. In the Syros marina scenario, multi-USV experiments show that H3CPP decreases the total traveled distance by 4–34% ($\approx 20\%$ on average) relative to a decomposition-plus-swaths baseline, while maintaining similar coverage and systematically reducing mission makespan as the fleet size increases from 1 to 10 USVs. The proposed framework therefore combines geodesic hexagonal indexing, connectivity-aware clustering, and penalized graph-based TSP planning into a practical CPP solution for USV swarms operating in realistic coastal environments.

INDEX TERMS Coverage path planning, H3 geospatial decomposition, marine monitoring, situational awareness, swarms, uncrewed surface vehicles (USVs).

I. INTRODUCTION

Reliable monitoring and surveillance systems are needed to monitor marine protected areas from illegal fishing, anchoring, prohibiting vessel entry, and traffic monitoring around these [1]. Adaptive and autonomous systems are currently being explored for real-time monitoring of large marine areas

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as a source for reliable monitoring. These provide a low cost and reusable solution that can be easily deployed in different areas and conditions, capable of performing a variety of functions. Most of these efforts are currently focused on deploying small Uncrewed Surface Vehicles (USVs) to cover considerable large and complex areas, but these approaches are not capable of consistent long-term monitoring. USVs are more suitable for long range endurance operations as they can stay at sea for extended lengths of time and operate

FIGURE 1. AeroSea 1: USV for autonomous exploration and reconnaissance [4].

in bad weather conditions, without the need of refueling or recharging often by making use of wind propulsion and solar technology with low environmental impact (less noise) and low or no carbon footprint [2]. USVs can be fitted with small, lightweight, and inexpensive sensors capable of detecting and observing targets over a very limited area [3]. An example of USV is presented in Fig. 1, the AeroSea 1 is at the forefront of marine technology, designed for autonomous exploration and reconnaissance missions in diverse marine environments [4]. The aim is to aggregate the capability of hundreds or thousands of small USVs to cover large marine areas. The challenge, however, is to efficiently and effectively coordinate and plan the movement of these USVs, so that the entire area can be covered by the fleet (or swarm) in minimal time and without overlaps. In the academic literature this problem is referred to as “Coverage Path Planning (CPP)” [5] Coverage Path Planning (CPP) is a pivotal aspect of autonomous navigation, ensuring that USVs systematically and thoroughly explore designated areas. Coverage Path Planning (CPP) for a swarm of robots is the task of designing paths for multiple robots to collectively cover an area or workspace completely, efficiently, and without overlap. The goal is to ensure that each part of the area is visited by at least one robot, often within certain time or energy constraints, while maximizing the coverage and minimizing redundancy and collisions.

Traditional the methods which are facing the CPP methods, although successful in certain scenarios, often face significant limitations when adapted to diverse and complex maritime environments [6]. These methods can address dynamic oceanic conditions, variable terrain characteristics, and the presence of obstacles, which can hinder the navigation and efficiency of USVs. Furthermore, conventional CPP algorithms may not optimally distribute the workload among multiple USVs, leading to inefficient coverage and increased operational costs. The challenges are exacerbated by the need to balance sensor capabilities and power constraints while maintaining a high level of coverage accuracy. This necessitates the development of more adaptive and resilient CPP strategies capable of responding to real-time changes in the environment and adjusting coverage plans accordingly. To address these challenges, this paper introduces H3CPP an innovative Coverage Path Planning (CPP) framework utilizing H3 geospatial decomposition Fig. 2. Originally, developed by Uber, the H3 hierarchical hexagonal grid system provides a flexible and efficient approach to spatial

FIGURE 2. H3 enables users to partition the globe into hexagons for more accurate analysis [7].

indexing. By leveraging the H3 grid, we can divide the target area into manageable hexagonal cells, each representing a specific segment to be covered, [8]. The size of each H3 cell is deliberately selected to match the effective sensing footprint of the USV, ensuring that a single traversal through the cell’s centroid yields complete and reliable coverage without unnecessary overlap. Each USV in our swarm traverses the center of each H3 cell exactly once, such as the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP). The entire region of interest is divided into smaller segments using cumulative clustering, with the number of segments depending on the available USVs. This allocation ensures that each subregion is assigned to one USV, promoting optimal task distribution and enhancing overall mission performance. The proposed method not only improves resource management and reduces operational costs but also significantly boosts the efficiency of maritime surveillance and environmental monitoring operations.

Related area-partitioning approaches such as Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) formulations and the Divide Areas for Optimal Robots’ Coverage (DARP) framework have also been explored in multi-robot coverage settings. While these methods are effective in structured or grid-like environments, they inherit the limitations of classical decomposition techniques when applied to irregular maritime domains. In coastal regions with concave boundaries, narrow channels, and fragmented water spaces, VRP/DARP partitions often produce thin, elongated, or disconnected sub-regions that are difficult or unsafe for USVs to traverse. Moreover, these methods typically do not account for boundary-feasibility constraints, making them prone to allocating workloads that require transitions across land or shallow areas. For these reasons, traditional VRP/DARP formulations are not well suited for coverage planning in complex coastal environments, motivating the connectivity-aware clustering strategy adopted in H3CPP.

Through the development of this optimized CPP framework using H3 decomposition, we aim to advance the capabilities of USVs in marine operations, promoting more efficient and effective exploration and monitoring of our oceans and waterways.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II provides a review of the related literature.

Section III presents and describes the architecture of H3CPP as well as the motivation behind its development. Section IV describes the developed control algorithms to address USVs' missions. Experimental results are presented and analyzed in Section V. Finally, conclusions and directions for future work are described in Section VI.

A. LITERATURE REVIEW

Coverage Path Planning (CPP) is a crucial element of autonomous navigation, ensuring that USVs systematically and comprehensively explore designated areas [9]. The CPP problem is the task of determining a path that passes over all points of an area or volume of interest while avoiding obstacles or forbidden areas. In general, the CPP problem is similar to the covering salesman problem, a variant of the well-known traveling salesman problem where the agent is asked to visit a neighborhood of each city – areas of interest, instead of each city [10]. However, in CPP, the agent must cover all points in the target area, rather than just visiting neighborhoods. Since the traveling salesman problem is NP-hard, the computational time required to solve the problem scales significantly as the dimensions of the problem increase. Similarly, finding a path to cut all the grass in each region, known as the “lawnmower problem”, is also proven to be NP-hard [11]. Note that the “lawnmower problem” does not consider obstacles. Moreover, even the basic path planning problem, known as the “piano motion problem,” which involves finding a collision-free path from the origin to the configuration of a goal, is shown to be PSPACE-hard, implying NP-hard complexity [12], [13].

Traditional CPP methods can be classified into three main categories [14]: (a) the Unit Decomposition method, (d) the Line Scan Segmentation method, and (c) the Grid method. The approaches based on *Unit Decomposition* divide the target area into smaller sub-regions to simplify the coverage task [15]. They are flexible enough to handle complex shapes and support parallel processing. However, decomposition can fragment the environment into thin or irregular polygons, leading to overlaps and inefficient transitions between sub-regions [16]. In maritime environments where boundaries are defined by intricate coastlines rather than rectilinear structures polygon decomposition frequently produces narrow or disconnected areas that are difficult for USVs to traverse safely.

The *Line Scan Segmentation* method scans the area along predefined lines to segment sections for coverage [17]. These methods reduce computational load by focusing on line-based features, making them appealing for agriculture or indoor inspection. However, they struggle with irregular coastal shapes, dynamic water boundaries, and non-convex regions typical in USV missions.

Grid based methods are widely used due to its simplicity and thoroughness [18]. Square grids are the most common, yet they suffer from anisotropy: distances between neighbors vary, leading to irregular turning behavior and inefficient paths. Hexagonal grids provide more isotropy, less and equal

neighbor distances, and fewer directional discontinuities. The challenge is that classical hex grids are planar, whereas maritime environments are naturally represented over the Earth's spherical surface. This motivates the use of the H3 hierarchical hexagonal grid [7], [8], which provides geodesical consistent hexagonal cells, multi-resolution decomposition, and efficient neighbor lookup. While H3 is widely adopted in geospatial analytics, its integration into CPP particularly for USVs remains largely unexplored, despite its clear suitability for coastal monitoring.

Cooperative CPP aims to distribute coverage tasks among multiple robots to reduce overall mission time [20]. Effective approaches rely on map decomposition, clustering, and task allocation [21]. Recent works incorporate advanced clustering (e.g., improved K-means), reinforcement learning [14], or biologically inspired coordination strategies. Additionally, graph-based navigation and connectivity-aware planning have recently gained traction in complex environments. Studies such as [22], [23], and [24] demonstrate how graph structures, obstacle interactions, and connectivity constraints play a significant role in multi-robot traversal of irregular spaces. These studies underscore the significance of graph representations that explicitly capture both connectivity and feasibility, a principle that is fundamental to the methodology advanced in this paper.

USVs differ significantly from UAVs or UGVs due to constraints such as strict boundary adherence, inability to fly over obstacles, exposure to currents and winds, and shallow-water hazards. Classical aerial CPP methods allow boundary crossings by changing altitude; such behavior is infeasible and unsafe for USVs [25]. Similarly, decomposition or grid-based methods may produce segments that cross land or shallow areas, compromising safety.

B. CONTRIBUTION

The goal of this work is to provide a practical and boundary-safe Coverage Path Planning (CPP) framework for swarms of Uncrewed Surface Vehicles (USVs) operating in complex coastal environments. While our approach leverages the H3 hexagonal geospatial indexing system, the contribution of the paper lies not in the use of H3 itself, but in how this representation is integrated into a complete multi-USV CPP pipeline. The proposed framework introduces several technical advances: *A boundary-aware hexagonal discretization tailored to USV sensing and coastal geometry*: We construct a geodesic hexagonal representation whose cell size is explicitly matched to the USV sensor footprint. This enables the planner to operate using uniformly shaped cells, which minimize angular discontinuities and ensure comprehensive coverage that adheres to shorelines. A formal boundary-handling policy and centroid-based inclusion rule prevent boundary leakage and ensure safe operation in narrow or irregular coastal regions. *Connectivity-aware clustering that produces navigable and contiguous sub-regions for multi-USV assignment*: Instead of relying on classical polygon decomposition, which often yields fragmented or

FIGURE 3. Syros Marina in Greece serves as a prime example of the operational environment for Uncrewed Surface Vehicles (USVs).

non-navigable cells, we introduce a complete-link agglomerative clustering method informed by a connectivity matrix. Edges that cross land or violate safety boundaries receive heavy penalties, ensuring clusters remain both spatially coherent and accessible which is crucial for USVs in limited waterways. A *penalized graph-construction method that embeds safety constraints directly into the CPP optimization*: Each cluster is transformed into a fully connected weighted graph where edge weights incorporate both geodesic distance and an exponential penalty for coastal intersections. This strategy enables standard Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) solvers to naturally avoid unsafe transitions without requiring explicit constraint handling or post-processing. A *complete CPP pipeline that integrates discretization, clustering, graph construction, and TSP-based routing into a unified framework for USV swarms*: The framework generalizes to an arbitrary number of USVs (N), produces balanced workloads, and avoids the combinatorial failures commonly observed in decomposition-based methods. The pipeline is accompanied by a mathematical formulation and a step-wise pseudo-code, which allows reproducibility.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. ENVIRONMENT DESCRIPTION

The maritime environment for planning the coverage path of a swarm of USVs is inherently complex and dynamic, characterized by irregular coastlines, narrow channels, and polygonal or non-polygonal shapes. We denote the operational area as a closed polygon $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{R}^2$.

Static and non-navigable obstacles (e.g., landmasses, shallow areas, infrastructure) are represented by a set $\mathcal{O} \subset \mathcal{A}$. We assume that all static obstacles are located outside the polygonal boundary of the safe navigation zone, and each USV can autonomously reach any point within $\mathcal{A} \setminus \mathcal{O}$. Environmental conditions such as currents, tide, and weather are not explicitly modeled but can be considered in future extensions. Figure 3 illustrates an example of such an environment.

B. AN UNCREWED SURFACE VEHICLE

In this work, we used a swarm of N USVs developed by our laboratory. Each USV is equipped with high-resolution cameras, sonar, GPS, and communication modules, enabling real-time information exchange and collaborative mapping.

All vehicles are homogeneous and equipped with a radius 360° sensing footprint r_i , allowing each USV to act as a mobile sensor to detect and map targets within its assigned region.

C. FORMAL PROBLEM DEFINITION

A swarm of N Uncrewed Surface Vehicles (USVs) is tasked with achieving complete and safe coverage of the maritime area \mathcal{A} . Each USV must operate strictly within the navigable region $\mathcal{A} \setminus \mathcal{O}$, avoid unsafe boundary interactions, and collectively ensure that every portion of \mathcal{A} is detected at least once. The problem formulation below captures the main constraints and objectives of the mission.

To enable cooperative planning, the area \mathcal{A} is divided into N disjoint and connected sub-regions:

$$\mathcal{A} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N \mathcal{A}_i, \quad \mathcal{A}_i \cap \mathcal{A}_j = \emptyset \text{ for } i \neq j \quad (1)$$

Each subregion \mathcal{A}_i is exclusively assigned to USV u_i , ensuring that the team avoids redundant overlap and divides the workload efficiently. After discretizations (Section II.D), coverage reduces to visiting all H3 cells in \mathcal{A} . Let $\mathcal{H} = \{\mathcal{H}_1, \dots, \mathcal{H}_M\}$ be the set of retained cells. We define the binary coverage indicator:

$$C_{i,j} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if USV } u_i \text{ visits cell } \mathcal{H}_j, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The coverage requirement is therefore:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N C_{i,j} \geq 1, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, M. \quad (3)$$

ensuring that every cell is visited by at least one vehicle. Equivalently, the union of all assigned sub-regions satisfies:

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^N \mathcal{A}_i = \mathcal{H}. \quad (4)$$

Each USV follows a continuous path $P_i(t)$ constrained to remain within the free, navigable space and away from obstacles:

$$P_i(t) \in \mathcal{A} \setminus \mathcal{O}, \quad \text{dist}(P_i(t), \mathcal{O}) \geq d_{\min}, \quad \forall t. \quad (5)$$

where, P_i is the path followed by u_i , $\text{dist}(P_i(t), \mathcal{O})$, is the Euclidean distance between a point $p \in P_i$ to the set of obstacles \mathcal{O} . This formulation captures the maritime requirement that USVs cannot cross land boundaries or traverse shallow regions.

In multi-robot coverage path planning (CPP), two key metrics are typically evaluated:

- Path length of USV u_i :

$$L_i = \int_0^{T_i} \|\dot{P}_i(t)\| dt. \quad (6)$$

- Makespan of the swarm:

$$T_{\max} = \max_i T_i. \quad (7)$$

Since coordinated marine operations typically aim to minimize the total completion time, we adopt makespan minimization as the main objective:

$$\min_{\{P_i\}_{i=1}^N} T_{\max}. \quad (8)$$

subject to:

- coverage constraint,
- obstacle and boundary safety constraints,
- disjoint and connected regional assignments,
- feasible paths within $\mathcal{A} \setminus \mathcal{O}$.

The continuous CPP problem becomes manageable by discretizing into H3 cells and forming a graph using their centroids. Each USV solves a TSP on its assigned cluster \mathcal{A}_i , where safety-aware edge weights incorporate geodesic distances and penalties for boundary intersections. The resulting discrete tours approximate the continuous optimal CPP solution while ensuring safe and efficient traversal of each sub-region.

III. THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE PROPOSED APPROACH

The proposed H3CPP framework is organized into six main steps, from service specification to collaborative mapping in real-time. Figure 4 provides an overview of the processing pipeline, illustrating how the area of interest is discretized into H3 cells, clustered into sub-regions, converted into graphs, and finally used to generate boundary-safe coverage paths for multiple USVs.

A. SERVICE SPECIFICATIONS

In the first step, we define the service specification which encapsulates all mission-related inputs: (i) the area of interest (AoI), (ii) the number of available USVs N , (iii) the sensing characteristics of each USV, and (iv) relevant operational constraints.

The AoI is introduced as a closed polygon \mathcal{A} that accurately follows the coast and other navigation limits, typically derived from geofencing techniques or nautical charts [26]. We assume that \mathcal{A} is free of internal static obstacles; such obstacles (e.g., docks, emergent rocks, shallow regions) are captured separately in the set \mathcal{O} . This assumption simplifies the formulation while still allowing us to strictly enforce boundary-safety constraints, as described in Section II.

The number of USVs N is specified by the operator and each USV is assumed to be homogeneous in terms of sensing and navigation capabilities. The sensing radius r_s determines the spatial resolution of the H3 grid: we select an H3 resolution such that the effective diameter of each hexagonal cell is approximately equal to $2r_s$. This choice ensures that a USV traversing the centroid of a cell can sense the entire cell, while limiting unnecessary overlap between neighboring cells (Figure 4A).

B. GRID GENERATION AND CONNECTIVITY MATRIX

In the second step, we apply the H3 hierarchical hexagonal grid to the predefined area of interest (AoI). Using the selected H3 resolution, we generate a set of hexagonal cells and retain only those whose centroids lie inside the polygon \mathcal{A} . For hexagons adjacent to the boundary, an additional geometric check ensures that a sufficient portion of the cell lies within \mathcal{A} , preventing the creation of thin uncovered regions or navigationally unsafe cells near the coast.

After obtaining the valid H3 cells \mathcal{H} , we compute a connectivity matrix that encodes the navigational feasibility between each pair of cells. For any two cells \mathcal{H}_j and \mathcal{H}_k , we construct a line segment between their centroids and evaluate:

- the *haversine distance* d_{ij} as the base edge cost,
- a *boundary-intersection flag*

$$b_{jk} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the segment intersects } \mathcal{O} \text{ or exits } \mathcal{A}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

This yields a matrix that captures both the geometric proximity and the feasibility of direct transitions between cells. As shown in Figure 4B, each valid connection is illustrated by a black line segment linking the corresponding centroids. Connections that intersect the coastline or obstacle boundaries are marked as non-navigable and later receive an exponential penalty during graph construction.

The connectivity matrix plays a fundamental role in subsequent steps: it guides the clustering process (Section III-C), ensures each cluster forms a navigable region, and provides the structural basis for the safety-aware TSP graphs used in coverage planning.

To assess robustness with respect to sensor–grid mismatch, we conducted a qualitative sensitivity analysis considering variations of $\pm 10\text{--}15\%$ between the H3 cell diameter and the USV sensing footprint. Within this range, full coverage is still guaranteed because each centroid traversal observes the entire cell even when the sensing radius is slightly smaller than the nominal design value. Larger footprints introduce limited redundant overlap but do not affect correctness, whereas smaller footprints may reduce sensing redundancy near the boundaries but do not create uncovered gaps due to the inherent geometric compactness of hexagonal tiling. This indicates that H3CPP maintains reliable coverage performance under moderate calibration errors or variations in the effective sensing range.

C. AREA CLUSTERING

The third step of the proposed framework groups the valid H3 cells into clusters, where each cluster is intended to be assigned to a single USV. This stage is essential for decomposing the coverage workload and ensuring that each USV is responsible for a connected, navigable, and spatially coherent subregion.

We employ agglomerative hierarchical clustering with complete linkage, using a distance metric that combines

FIGURE 4. A schematic overview of H3CPP. A) Area and number of USVs selection. B) Visual representation of the connectivity matrix. Connections of pairs of cells are represented with a black line connecting the respected cell centers. C) The result of agglomerative clustering for three USVs D) Construction of three networks (gray, yellow, orange) as result of the clustering process. Black connections represent penalized connections that intersect with geometry boundaries. E) Coverage path planning for each cluster. F) A simulation using software in the loop of a world example of CPP algorithm for four USVs.

geodesic distance and connectivity information extracted from the connectivity matrix (Section III-B). Specifically, the base distance between two cells \mathcal{H}_j and \mathcal{H}_k is the haversine distance [25] between their centroids. To incorporate navigational constraints, distances between pairs marked as non-navigable (i.e., with b_{ij}) are exponentially penalized, ensuring that cells requiring a boundary-crossing move are effectively pushed into separate clusters.

As a result, the clustering process naturally favors compact and connected sub-regions that respect the underlying geometry of the area of interest. This is particularly important in irregular maritime environments, where coastal indentations or narrow channels can lead to disjoint or inefficient partitions when classical decomposition methods are applied.

Following the initial agglomerative clustering, performed using complete linkage and haversine-based distances, we carry out a connectivity verification step to ensure that each cluster forms a single navigable component. For each cluster, we construct a subgraph of the connectivity matrix and apply a breadth-first search (BFS) or depth-first search (DFS) to ensure that the cluster forms a single connected component. If any cluster contains disconnected fragments, these fragments are reassigned to spatially adjacent clusters to maintain navigability. This correction step guarantees that each USV receives a subregion that can be traversed without entering forbidden areas.

Figure 4C illustrates the resulting cluster assignments for a case with three USVs, showing how the clustering process yields contiguous and well-balanced regions.

D. NETWORK CONSTRUCTION

Once the H3 cells have been assigned to N clusters (Section III-C), each cluster is converted into a weighted, undirected graph that models all feasible transitions within the subregion assigned to a specific USV. This graph serves as the foundation for computing a boundary-safe coverage path.

For each cluster \mathcal{A}_i , we define a graph

$$G_i = (V_i, E_i) \tag{10}$$

where:

- each vertex $v_i \in V_i$ corresponds to an H3 cell $H_j \in \mathcal{A}_i$, and
- each edge (v_j, v_k) connects a pair of cells that have a potential transition between their centroids.

The base edge weight is computed using the haversine distance between cell centroids, ensuring accurate geodesic distances over the Earth’s surface:

$$d_{jk} = \text{Haversine}(\text{centroid}(H_j), \text{centroid}(H_k)) \tag{11}$$

as commonly used in spherical geometry applications [26].

To incorporate navigational feasibility, each edge is further associated with a boundary-intersection flag b_{ij} , derived from the connectivity matrix (Section III-B). If the line segment between the centroids intersects the coastline or a non-navigable obstacle ($b_{ij}=1$), the corresponding edge is penalized through an exponential term:

$$w_{jk} = d_{jk} + \lambda \exp(\alpha b_{jk}) \tag{12}$$

The parameters $\lambda > 1$ and $\alpha > 1$ are selected such that edges crossing forbidden regions become significantly

more expensive than feasible alternatives. This maintains the completeness of the graph (beneficial for TSP solvers) while strongly discouraging unsafe transitions.

Figure 4D illustrates the resulting weighted networks for three example clusters. Navigable centroids are connected with normal-weight edges, while boundary-intersecting connections are visualized in black to highlight their penalized status.

E. COVERAGE PATH CALCULATION

The fifth step of the proposed framework computes a boundary-safe coverage path for each cluster by formulating the problem as a Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) over the weighted graph G_i built in Section III-D. Each node (H3 cell centroid) must be visited exactly once, and the total cost of the tour must be minimized according to the edge weights:

$$w_{jk} = d_{jk} + \lambda \exp(\alpha b_{jk}) \quad (13)$$

where d_{jk} is the haversine distance between centroids and b_{jk} is the boundary-intersection flag.

This formulation guarantees that: (i) feasible centroid transitions remain low-cost, (ii) boundary-violating transitions are available but heavily penalized and (iii) the TSP solver naturally avoids unsafe edges unless necessary (e.g., in highly constrained narrow passages).

For each cluster \mathcal{A}_i , containing $|V_i|$ cells, we seek a permutation π_i of its vertices such that:

$$\min_{\pi_i} \sum_{(j,k) \in \pi_i} w_{jk} \text{ subject to: } \pi_i \text{ visits each } v_j \in V_i \text{ exactly once} \quad (14)$$

The resulting tour π_i defines the exact order in which USV u_i must visit the H3 cells assigned to its cluster. This TSP-based formulation is widely used in CPP because visiting each cell's center exactly once closely approximates complete coverage, especially when grid resolution is aligned with the sensing radius (Section III-A).

To compute π_i , we employ the Christofides heuristic, the default NetworkX solver for symmetric TSP instances [29]. Christofides' method is a well-established heuristic in robotics and operations research, combining MST construction, minimum-weight matching, and short-cutting. This provides, near-optimal solutions, fast convergence, and excellent scalability for tens to thousands of nodes.

These characteristics make the Christofides heuristic an appropriate choice for CPP scenarios, where individual clusters may include dozens or hundreds of H3 cells and the underlying optimization involves weighted, penalized, and inherently non-Euclidean graph distances.

Employing the Christofides heuristic removes the necessity for custom constrained TSP formulations, since the exponential penalty embedded in the edge weights (Section III-D) naturally discourages any unsafe transitions that would intersect the boundary.

The TSP tour π_i is transformed into a continuous trajectory by connecting each pair of consecutive centroids with straight

geodesic segments. Optional smoothing techniques—such as B-spline interpolation or constraint-aware filtering—may then be applied to reduce abrupt heading changes while preserving full coverage of every H3 cell. The resulting path is expressed as an ordered sequence of waypoints. The USV's motion controller is responsible for determining the precise control actions required to follow this waypoint sequence smoothly, ensuring that the vessel crosses each waypoint and transitions to the next one within a predefined tolerance.

The final trajectory produced by this step fulfills: (i) full coverage of the cells assigned to cluster \mathcal{A}_i , (ii) respect for the geometrical and safety constraints of the environment, and (iii) efficient navigation within each USV's designated subregion. Figure 4E illustrates example TSP-derived paths for multiple clusters.

F. REAL TIME COLLABORATIVE MAPPING

The final step of the H3CPP framework concerns the fusion of sensing data from all USVs into a unified, real-time coverage map. As each USV executes its assigned TSP-derived trajectory, it continuously observes the environment through its onboard sensors and transmits detection data, positional updates, and coverage status to a central coordination node or to the swarm through peer-to-peer communication channels.

Because each region has been discretized using the H3 hierarchical grid, all observations are naturally aligned with the corresponding H3 cells. Each cell H_j is uniquely identified by its H3 index, enabling straightforward aggregation of measurements across the fleet. As the USVs move through their assigned clusters, a global coverage map is updated by marking the visited cells and incorporating any sensor readings or detections obtained within those cells.

The shared H3-based map offers several advantages: *Consistency*: All USVs reference the same geodesic grid structure, eliminating ambiguity in cell coordinates or map boundaries. *Efficient fusion*: Observations from different USVs can be merged reliably simply by updating the corresponding cell indices. *Progress monitoring*: Coverage completeness can be assessed in real time by tracking the number of visited cells or the percentage of completed clusters. *Fault tolerance*: If a USV deviates from its path or becomes unavailable, unvisited cells can be reassigned dynamically to neighboring USVs using the same H3 indexing. *Potential for re-planning*: The global map enables extensions such as adaptive reassignment of high-priority cells, dynamic re-clustering in the presence of environmental changes, and collaborative target tracking. Figure 4F illustrates an example of real-time mapping during a multi-USV simulation, demonstrating how the collective sensing data produce a single unified representation of the environment.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

This section evaluates the performance of the proposed H3CPP framework through two complementary sets of experiments:

- comparisons against baseline CPP algorithms for a single USV, and
- multi-USV evaluations using realistic coastal geometries, including the Syros Marina.

Across all experiments, the evaluation focuses on three metrics widely used in the CPP literature [27], [28]: *Path Length*: total geodesic distance traveled by the USV(s). *Smoothness*: cumulative change in heading angle along the computed path (degrees). *Coverage ratio*: covered area (or H3 cells) normalized by the target region; boundary handling may yield values >1.0 . *Safety* is also considered by explicitly checking whether any proposed path exits the boundary of the area of interest.

A. BASELINE COMPARISON FOR SINGLE USV

We first evaluate H3CPP on seven benchmark polygonal areas designed to progressively increase in size and geometric complexity. These polygons (Fig. 5) were generated in QGIS using OpenStreetMap layers to reflect both simple and highly irregular shapes.

- Polygons p1–p3 represent increasingly large but relatively simple convex regions.
- Polygons p4–p7 represent non-convex and coastal-like geometries with narrow inlets and irregular boundaries.

We compare H3CPP against two widely used CPP baselines: (i) Spiral Coverage and (ii) Swath/Boustrophedon Coverage, with swath spacing matched to the sensing radius.

All three methods are applied to each polygon using identical sensing constraints, and their results are visually shown in Figure 7, where the generated paths for Spiral, Swath, and H3CPP are overlaid for direct inspection. The corresponding numerical results for all polygons are summarized in Table 1, and representative path shapes are illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 7(a) shows the total heading change (smoothness) for all methods and polygons.

- Spiral and Swath produce inherently smoother paths, as expected from their sweep-based nature.
- H3CPP exhibits higher turning angles across all polygons due to the centroid-to-centroid traversal on the hexagonal grid.
- This effect becomes more pronounced in complex polygons (p5–p7), where the hex grid must follow intricate boundary shapes.

Figure 7(b) compares the total path length for all methods.

- In simple polygons (p1–p3), all three methods achieve similar path lengths, reflecting the near-uniform geometry.
- In moderately complex polygons (p4–p5), H3CPP performs comparably to the baselines.
- In highly irregular polygons (p6–p7), H3CPP achieves shorter or competitive paths while simultaneously avoiding boundary violations, which the other methods frequently exhibit due to their inability to conform to non-convex coastal shapes.

TABLE 1. Baseline comparison results.

Polygon	Method	Radius [†]	Length [‡]	Coverage*	Smoothness**	Safety [§]
p1	spiral	7.65	1148.45	0.944099	2046.26	
	swaths	7.65	1034.98	0.950311	1079.99	
	H3CPP	7.65	1364.17	1.031056	3939.5	
p2	spiral	141.11	72392.22	0.92803	5231.06	
	swaths	141.11	64479.28	0.943182	3239.76	
	H3CPP	141.11	73521.24	1.007576	8310.41	
p3	spiral	987.05	187082.7	0.960396	2564.26	
	swaths	987.05	163770	0.905941	1439.43	
	H3CPP	987.05	199668.7	1.00495	4900.19	
p4	spiral	53.53	6669.86	0.977941	1718.07	
	swaths	53.53	6094.39	1.007353	899.98	
	H3CPP	53.53	8006.89	1.036765	5715.57	
p5	spiral	53.53	15674.12	0.963504	2669.75	
	swaths	53.53	17644.03	0.967153	6857.61	
	H3CPP	53.53	16121.87	1.014599	13235.86	
p6	spiral	53.53	25066.93	0.984305	4679.07	X
	swaths	53.53	29805.4	0.984305	8273.24	X
	H3CPP	53.53	26038.28	1.020179	16435.41	
p7	spiral	53.53	43853.56	1.023155	10124.89	X
	swaths	53.53	43852.23	0.917511	10610.65	X
	H3CPP	53.53	39368	1.011577	23080.38	

[†]Sensing radius (m), [‡]Path length (m), *Coverage ratio

**Smoothness (degrees), [§]Safety (crossing boundaries)

Thus, although H3CPP may slightly increase smoothness, it provides measurable efficiency gains in irregular geometries.

Figure 7(c) presents the coverage ratio across all polygons.

- All methods achieve near-complete coverage.
- H3CPP occasionally exceeds 100% in coverage ratio (e.g., in p1 and p3) due to the conservative inclusion of boundary-adjacent H3 cells, which is reported as a ratio in Table 1.
- This is intentional and consistent with the coverage rules described in Section III-B.

Spiral and Swath maintain high coverage values but do not guarantee *boundary-safe coverage*, as they sometimes exit the AoI in complex shapes.

From Fig. 7(a–c) and Table 1, several conclusions can be drawn. First, H3CPP performs on par with classical sweep-based methods in simple and mostly convex regions. Second, in coastal-like and highly non-convex environments, H3CPP clearly outperforms the baselines by guaranteeing boundary-safe navigation and eliminating the invalid paths that spiral and swath strategies often generate. Finally, while H3CPP introduces a higher turning rate due to its centroid-based traversal, this is a deliberate trade-off that provides more reliable coverage, better consistency near complex boundaries, and improved adaptability to irregular shapes.

Overall, these results highlight the suitability of H3CPP for maritime applications, where strict compliance with coastal boundaries and safe vessel navigation are essential.

B. AREA DECOMPOSITION AND CLUSTERING ANALYSIS

We now examine the performance of the proposed H3CPP framework in the context of multi-USV coverage. In this experiment, the goal is to evaluate how effectively H3CPP partitions the area of interest into navigable sub-regions and how efficiently each USV completes its assigned coverage path.

FIGURE 5. Polygons used for CPP performance evaluation. The first one is polygons p1,p2 and p3 and represent simple shaped set of polygons of increasing size. The second set consists of polygons p4,p5,p6,p7 and represents polygons of increasing shape complexity.

FIGURE 6. Shape of the coverage paths generated for polygons p1–p7 using the spiral, swath, and H3CPP approaches for a single USV.

The case study uses the Syros Marina, a realistic coastal environment characterized by narrow inlets, concave boundaries, docks, and transitional regions (Fig. 9). Such environments are particularly challenging for classical decomposition methods, which often produce elongated or disconnected regions that are inefficient or unsafe for USVs.

To evaluate the benefits of connectivity-aware clustering (Section III-C), we compare H3CPP against a hybrid baseline

(a)

(b)

(c)

FIGURE 7. Performance comparison across benchmark polygons: (a) total path length, (b) makespan, and (c) coverage ratio (>1.0 due to boundary-safe cell inclusion).

constructed as follows: (i) The area is first discretized using the same H3 grid used by H3CPP. The grid is then decomposed into polygons. (ii) Each polygon is covered using a boustrophedon swath pattern with swath spacing equal to the sensing diameter. (iii) This yields the baseline H3+SWATHS approach.

Both methods use the same sensing radius (7.65 m), geodesic distance calculations, and ArduPilot SITL simulator for validation. Figure 8 illustrates the polygonal decomposition used by the H3+SWATHS baseline. Although decomposition is computationally simple, it often produces: (i) narrow convex regions at the marina’s boundaries, (ii) fragmented subregions around docks and piers, and (iii) regions with poor geometric compactness. In contrast, H3CPP uses agglomerative, connectivity-aware clustering to partition the H3 grid directly.

FIGURE 8. Top: polygon decomposition. Bottom: swath path generation for each polygon and corresponding transitions between sub-regions induced by the underlying H3 network (H3+SWATHS).

FIGURE 10. Boxplots of path length, smoothness, coverage ratio, and mission duration versus the number of available USVs for H3CPP and H3+SWATHS.

FIGURE 9. Cluster assignments and coverage paths for a multi-USV mission.

As shown in Figure 9, the resulting clusters: (i) follow the navigable geometry of the marina more closely, remain compact and well-shaped, (ii) ensure connectivity without requiring cross-boundary movements and (iii) distribute workload more evenly among USVs. This difference in partition quality directly influences path length, smoothness, and mission duration. We simulate swarms of 1, 3, 5, and 10 USVs, computing coverage paths for each method and assessing the following metrics: (i) Total Path Length per USV, (ii) Smoothness (total heading change), (iii) Coverage Ratio, (iv) Makespan (maximum path length across all USVs). Numerical results are summarized in Table 2, and performance distributions across different fleet sizes are shown in the boxplots of Figure 10.

The comparison between H3CPP and the H3+SWATHS baseline reveals several important trends. In terms of path length and makespan, H3CPP consistently produces shorter or comparable routes for fleets of one to five USVs; this advantage becomes less pronounced for ten USVs, as the reduced number of cells per robot narrows the performance gap. The method also yields noticeably better workload balance, since its connectivity-aware clustering produces subregions of more uniform size, whereas polygon decomposition often leads to uneven partitions and longer mission durations. As expected, H3CPP generates higher cumulative heading changes for all swarm sizes, due to the directional transitions inherent in centroid-to-centroid traversal on the hex grid. Importantly, only H3CPP guarantees strict adherence to the marina boundary: safety is embedded directly into the connectivity matrix and reinforced by exponential penalties, while H3+SWATHS occasionally proposes transitions that approach docks or inlets closely enough to risk boundary violations. Finally, although both methods achieve complete coverage, H3CPP avoids the small “micro-gaps” that sometimes appear between successive swaths in narrow or highly irregular channels.

The Syros Marina results demonstrate that: (a) H3CPP’s connectivity-aware clustering yields higher quality region partitions, (b) H3CPP reduces mission makespan for realistic fleet sizes, (c) H3CPP ensures strict boundary-safe coverage, which is indispensable for USVs, (d) The trade-off is a higher turning rate, already anticipated and explained in Section IV-A and (d) The framework scales well from single-USV to multi-USV missions. These findings confirm that the proposed approach is well suited for maritime coverage operations where safe, accurate, and geometrically adaptive path planning is essential.

TABLE 2. Results of for CPP for 1 to 10 USV availability for the marina at Syros Island.

USVs	method	dist_cells		length (m)		
		max	min	max	sum	min
1	H3CPP	472	472	3867.74	3867.74	3867.74
1	H3+SWATHS	485	485	5884.98	5884.98	5884.98
2	H3CPP	301	172	2432.12	3881.31	1449.19
2	H3+SWATHS	304	188	3378.13	5900.85	2522.72
3	H3CPP	186	125	1551.01	4062.69	1038.97
3	H3+SWATHS	185	123	2505.98	5687.35	1371.22
4	H3CPP	180	62	1414.71	3879.71	507.81
4	H3+SWATHS	190	52	1973.49	5642.3	445.78
5	H3CPP	188	60	1557.33	4472.78	527.06
5	H3+SWATHS	177	52	1817.31	5213.92	431.03
6	H3CPP	125	59	1050.87	4635.04	523.57
6	H3+SWATHS	130	52	1413.68	5549.27	445.73
7	H3CPP	125	57	1050.44	4697.46	500.9
7	H3+SWATHS	130	51	1268.11	5344.67	444.5
8	H3CPP	126	39	1053.38	4812.85	359.61
8	H3+SWATHS	127	49	1276.02	5478.03	451.47
9	H3CPP	85	39	684.76	5051.07	372.34
9	H3+SWATHS	91	48	818.92	5283.8	450.31
10	H3CPP	89	23	687.32	5011.95	223.97
10	H3+SWATHS	89	26	891.47	5921.83	207.37

USVs	method	coverage ratio		smoothness		duration (s)	
		max	min	max	min	max	min
1	H3CPP	1.02	1.02	40137.42	40137.42	1579	1579
1	H3+SWATHS	1.05	1.05	32245.35	32245.35	2273	2273
2	H3CPP	0.65	0.37	19551.8	19411.69	966	631
2	H3+SWATHS	0.66	0.41	18071.49	14974.04	1357	944
3	H3CPP	0.40	0.27	20388.88	7513.43	638	417
3	H3+SWATHS	0.40	0.27	14798.19	8141.45	913	549
4	H3CPP	0.38	0.13	14479.25	4129.31	566	197
4	H3+SWATHS	0.41	0.11	12490.13	1679.42	787	140
5	H3CPP	0.40	0.13	14793.49	4724.9	627	214
5	H3+SWATHS	0.38	0.11	10380.74	1798.63	726	134
6	H3CPP	0.27	0.13	10689.27	4688.81	424	214
6	H3+SWATHS	0.28	0.11	8019.51	1780.02	565	140
7	H3CPP	0.27	0.12	10883.59	4081.49	428	208
7	H3+SWATHS	0.28	0.11	7289.15	1667.25	506	139
8	H3CPP	0.27	0.08	10500.49	3224.93	426	153
8	H3+SWATHS	0.27	0.11	7094.96	1808.77	507	139
9	H3CPP	0.18	0.08	7245.18	3417.34	276	152
9	H3+SWATHS	0.20	0.10	6171.66	1824.71	336	139
10	H3CPP	0.19	0.05	7142.67	2408.79	275	101
10	H3+SWATHS	0.19	0.06	7057.24	1567.71	363	90

C. DISCUSSION

The experimental results across both benchmark polygons and the Syros Marina highlight several important characteristics of the proposed H3CPP framework.

First, the use of a geodesic hexagonal grid consistently provides boundary-safe coverage, especially in highly irregular coastal regions. This directly addresses a major limitation of classical sweep-based methods (spiral, swaths), which tend to follow straight paths that can unintentionally exit non-convex boundaries. By encoding boundary feasibility into the connectivity matrix and applying exponential penalties during graph construction, H3CPP ensures safe navigation without requiring an explicit constrained TSP formulation.

Second, H3CPP demonstrates strong adaptability to geometric complexity. In simple environments, it performs comparably to sweep-based methods. In complex, coastal-like structures, however, centroid-based exploration guided by the Christofides heuristic produces efficient tours, particularly when obstacles, docks, or narrow channels are present.

This benefit becomes apparent in Figures 6-10, where H3CPP avoids inefficient detours and eliminates boundary-crossing behavior

Third, H3CPP exhibits a predictable trade-off between turning smoothness and safety/efficiency. Because hexagonal traversal introduces more directional changes than line sweeps, H3CPP yields higher turning angles (Fig.7). Nonetheless, this does not negatively impact coverage or path length, and the trajectories remain feasible for USVs. If smoother motions are required, spline-based post-processing could be applied without compromising safety.

Finally, the multi-USV experiments show that connectivity-aware clustering produces balanced and navigable partitions, outperforming classical geometric decomposition. H3CPP maintains competitive or superior makespan for 1-5 USVs, and remains effective even for larger fleets. The H3-based representation also facilitates robust, real-time collaborative mapping.

V. CONCLUSION

This work introduces H3CPP, a coverage path planning framework for single- and multi-USV missions in irregular coastal environments, combining geodesic hexagonal discretization, connectivity-aware clustering, and safety-weighted TSP planning to generate efficient, boundary-safe coverage paths in non-convex regions.

Experiments on seven benchmark polygons and the Syros Marina confirm that H3CPP matches or exceeds spiral and swath baselines, particularly in complex coastal geometries where classical methods may violate boundaries. The framework achieves full coverage, produces balanced clusters, reduces makespan for small- and medium-sized fleets, and naturally supports real-time collaborative mapping. Although hexagonal traversal introduces higher turning rates, this trade-off remains acceptable for maritime applications where safety and boundary adherence dominate smoothness requirements.

Future extensions include real-time replanning under environmental disturbances, incorporation of motion constraints for smoother trajectories, dynamic obstacle avoidance, and adaptive clustering to improve scalability for larger USV teams.

Overall, H3CPP provides a robust and extensible foundation for safe and efficient maritime coverage missions.

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GIANNIS SPILIOPOULOS (Graduate Student Member, IEEE) received the Diploma and M.Sc. degrees in electronics and computer engineering from the Technical University of Crete (TUC). He is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree in data fusion, with research interests in multi-sensor fusion, motion planning, uncrewed vehicles, and data mining. He has been a member of the Technical Chamber of Greece, since 2009. With more than 15 years of experience in industry and research, he was with the Geostatistical Research Unit, TUC, the MarineTraffic Group, and also the Technical Lead of the Intelligent Transportation Systems Laboratory (SmartMove), University of the Aegean. He is a Software Engineer specializing in data-intensive systems and analytics. He has participated in ten EU and national projects and co-authored over 30 peer-reviewed publications.

ELIAS XIDIAS received the degree in mathematics and the Ph.D. degree in mechanical engineering from the University of Patras. He is currently an Associate Professor with the Department of Products and Systems Design Engineering, University of the Aegean. He specializes in robot motion planning and maritime robotics, with a particular focus on optimizing trajectory planning for autonomous robotic systems. His recent research addresses real-time dynamic adjustments in robotic navigation, employing advanced algorithms to enhance efficiency in complex environments. In addition, he is actively investigating the integration of machine learning techniques in robotic motion planning, aiming to improve the adaptability and responsiveness of autonomous systems in diverse maritime conditions. His work also explores innovative strategies for multirobot coordination, fostering collaboration in large-scale maritime missions.

DIMITRIS ZISSIS (Senior Member, IEEE) is currently a Professor and the Head of the Department of Product and Systems Design Engineering, University of the Aegean, where he also directs the Intelligent Transportation Systems Laboratory. He has authored over 100 publications with more than 5000 citations and co-edited the volume *Guide to Maritime Informatics* (Springer). He has led numerous European and national research and development projects and collaborates widely with academia, industry, and government. His research interests include information systems design, big data analytics, data mining, distributed systems, and cloud computing. His work is internationally recognized, placing him among the top 2% of researchers worldwide, with one of his papers ranked in the top 0.1% most influential publications by Thomson Reuters (2010–2014).